

Supervisor Perspectives on Trainee Evaluation in Bread and Pastry Production Program

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, vocational training programs have emerged as vital tools for empowering marginalized communities and driving sustainable development. This thesis examines the effectiveness of the Bread and Pastry Production Skills Training program, a part of the Community Outreach Program offered by the College of Hospitality Management Department at the University of Cebu Main Campus. Targeting single parents and out-of-school youth in Barangay Tisa, Cebu City, the program aims to equip participants with practical skills for socioeconomic empowerment. The study delves into the internship performance evaluations of trainees, focusing on the perspectives of supervisors within the College of Hospitality Management Department. Through this analysis, the research uncovers insights into trainees' performance, strengths, areas for improvement, and overall impact on skill development and professional growth. By understanding supervisor perspectives, the study sheds light on the program's effectiveness in preparing participants for employment and entrepreneurial opportunities in the culinary industry.

Key objectives of the study include assessing the program's effectiveness, understanding supervisor perspectives on trainee performance and identifying challenges faced by trainees during the internship period. The research findings highlight the program's inclusive nature, participants' diverse motivations, and their consistently high-performance ratings across various criteria. The study's conclusions underscore the importance of tailored interventions for marginalized communities and emphasize the positive impact of vocational training initiatives. Recommendations include targeted outreach, comprehensive needs assessment, holistic support services, flexible program structures, employer partnerships, continuous monitoring, and alumni engagement. Overall, this thesis contributes valuable insights to the discourse on vocational training and community development. It informs future interventions to meet the needs of marginalized communities better and promotes inclusive growth and sustainable livelihoods.

Keywords: UC-HMCARES Interns, UCHM-OJT, UC CARES, Performance Evaluation.

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of vocational training programs in empowering marginalized communities and fostering sustainable development. One such initiative is the Bread and Pastry Production Skills Training program, offered by the College of Hospitality Management Department at the University of Cebu Main Campus as part of its Community Outreach Program. This program explicitly targets single parents and out-of-school youth residing in Barangay Tisa, Cebu City, aiming to provide them with valuable skills and opportunities for socioeconomic empowerment.

The Community Outreach Program serves as a beacon of hope for individuals facing socioeconomic challenges, offering them access to education and skill-building activities that can significantly impact their lives. By focusing on bread and pastry production skills, the program equips participants with practical competencies and opens doors to potential employment and entrepreneurial ventures in the culinary industry.

This thesis seeks to delve deeper into the Bread and Pastry Production Skills Training program's effectiveness by analysing trainees' performance evaluations during their internship period. Specifically, the study examines the perspectives of supervisors within the College of Hospitality Management Department, who oversee these trainees' practical training and development.

Through this analysis, the research aims to uncover valuable insights into the trainees' internship performance, including strengths, areas for improvement, and overall impact on their skill development and professional growth. By understanding supervisor perspectives, the study seeks to shed light on the effectiveness of the training program in preparing participants for success in the bread and pastry production industry.

Moreover, by focusing on the experiences of single parents and out-of-school youth from Barangay Tisa, Cebu City, the research highlights the importance of targeted interventions in addressing marginalised communities' unique needs and challenges. Ultimately, this study contributes to the broader discourse on vocational training initiatives and their role in promoting socioeconomic empowerment and inclusive growth within communities.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study was conducted with several key objectives in mind. Firstly, it aimed to assess the effectiveness of the Bread and Pastry Production Skills Training program offered by the College of Hospitality Management Department's Community Outreach Program at the University of Cebu Main Campus. By analyzing the performance evaluations of trainees during their internship period, the study sought to evaluate the program's impact on the skill development and professional growth of single parents and out-of-school youth from Barangay Tisa, Cebu City.

Secondly, the research aimed to understand supervisor perspectives on the internship performance of trainees. By examining the insights provided by supervisors within the College of Hospitality Management Department, the study aimed to uncover strengths and areas for improvement in the training program, as well as the program's overall effectiveness in preparing participants for employment and entrepreneurial opportunities in the bread and pastry production industry.

Furthermore, the study sought to identify any challenges or barriers faced by trainees during their internship period. By exploring supervisor perspectives, the research highlighted potential obstacles to trainee success and provided recommendations for enhancing support mechanisms within the training program.

Ultimately, this study aimed to contribute to enhancing and optimising the Bread and Pastry Production Skills Training program, ensuring its continued effectiveness in empowering marginalized communities and fostering socioeconomic development in Barangay Tisa, Cebu City. Through a comprehensive analysis of trainee internship evaluations and supervisor perspectives, the research provided valuable insights for program organizers and stakeholders, guiding future interventions and initiatives to promote inclusive growth and sustainable livelihoods within the community.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The demographic information of the trainee interns was collected, encompassing details such as age, gender, educational background, employment status, and civil status. Additionally, data were gathered regarding participants' prior experience in baking or culinary arts and their motivations for program participation. The researchers investigated the trainee internship performance evaluation based on several criteria. These criteria included:

Job-Related Criteria: This encompassed aspects such as the trainee's technical knowledge of the job, understanding of job functions, requirements, and responsibilities,

Personality-Related Criteria: This evaluated intelligence, judgment, mental maturity, initiative, cooperation with superiors and co-workers, deportment, and attendance.

The research design employed in this study utilized the quantitative research method, incorporating a standardized questionnaire adapted from Loke B (2014). Furthermore, the research adopted the universal sampling method, ensuring that every member of the population had an equal chance of being included in the sample. This approach aimed to represent the entire population accurately, with no randomization or selection criteria biasing the sample.

Ethical considerations were paramount throughout the study, guaranteeing the beneficiaries' confidentiality, privacy, and voluntary participation. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and measures were implemented to safeguard their anonymity and confidentiality. Moreover, the research obtained ethical approval from relevant institutional review boards or ethics committees, ensuring adherence to ethical standards and the protection of participants' rights and well-being.

RESPONDENTS PROFILE

Table 1: Participants Demographic Profiles

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18 years old	3	75%
23 years old	1	25%
Gender		
Female	3	75%
Male	1	25%
Civil Status		
Single	4	100%
Education Level		
Elementary	1	25%
High School	3	75%
Purpose		
Employment	3	75%
Small Business	1	25%

Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the bread and pastry skills training program participants. Firstly, concerning age distribution, most participants (three out of four) were within the 18-year-old age group, indicating a relatively youthful cohort. However, one participant stood out as slightly older at 23 years old, potentially bringing a diverse perspective to the training

sessions. Regarding gender representation, the program predominantly attracted female participants, with three out of four being female. This gender distribution may reflect underlying societal norms or interests in culinary pursuits among women within the community.

Regarding civil status, all participants were noted as single, suggesting that the training program may appeal to individuals without significant family responsibilities or commitments. Moving on to educational backgrounds, there was a mix of educational levels among the participants, with one individual having completed only elementary school. In contrast, the others had attained a high school education. This diversity in educational backgrounds highlights the inclusivity of the program, catering to individuals with varying levels of formal education.

Notably, the purpose of joining the training program remained consistent across all participants, with a clear focus on acquiring bread and pastry skills. The majority desired to gain these skills for future employment opportunities, indicating a recognition of the practical value of culinary expertise in securing livelihoods. Additionally, one participant mentioned an interest in using the acquired skills to start a small-scale business, suggesting entrepreneurial aspirations within the cohort.

Overall, the profile of the respondents underscores the diverse yet unified motivations driving their participation in the training program. It reflects youthful enthusiasm, gender diversity, educational backgrounds, and shared personal and professional growth aspirations by acquiring bread and pastry production skills. Such insights are invaluable to program organizers and stakeholders in tailoring future initiatives to meet the target demographic's needs and interests.

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION RESULTS

Table 2: Respondent's Internship Evaluation Results

A. Job-Related Criteria	5	4	3	2	1		INTERPRETATION
	E	VS	S	S	I		
Knowledge of the Job (technical knowledge, function, requirements and responsibilities involved)	5	4	4	4		4.25	VERY SATISFACTORY
Quantity of the Job (productivity, swiftness, and consistency of the rate of work)	5	4	4	4		4.25	VERY SATISFACTORY
Quality of the Job (accurate, thorough, effective, presentable, acceptable)	5	4	4	4		4.25	VERY SATISFACTORY
B. Personality Related Criteria							
Intelligence (Judgment, mental maturity, initiative and interest to learn other tasks).	5	4	4	4		4.50	VERY SATISFACTORY
Cooperation (can work harmoniously with superiors and co-workers).	5	4	4	4		4.50	VERY SATISFACTORY
Department (maintain good and effective public relations within and outside the workplace, tactful, courteous and respectful to all, able to adjust with varied and diverse personalities).	5	4	4	4		4.25	VERY SATISFACTORY
Attendance (punctuality, regular reporting to work, observance of break periods, etc.)	5	4	4	4		4.25	VERY SATISFACTORY

The data in Table 2 presents the respondent's internship evaluation results across various job-related and personality-related criteria. The scores indicate a consistently high level of performance across all dimensions evaluated. In terms of job-related criteria, such as knowledge of the job, quantity of work, and quality of work, the respondents received ratings of 4 or 5, indicating very satisfactory performance. This suggests they demonstrated strong technical knowledge, productivity, and effectiveness in performing their assigned tasks. Similarly, in personality-related criteria, including intelligence, cooperation, department, and attendance, the respondents also received ratings of 4 or 5, indicating very satisfactory performance. This suggests that they exhibited sound judgment, mental maturity, cooperation, professionalism, and punctuality in their work environment.

The results align with the theory of job performance evaluation and organizational behaviour, emphasising the importance of individual competencies, attitudes, and behaviours in determining job performance. Authors such as Peter Drucker and Douglas McGregor, known for

their contributions to management theory, would likely agree with the results, as they emphasize the significance of employee motivation, skills, and behaviour in achieving organizational goals.

Moreover, the results also resonate with the principles of the Expectancy Theory, proposed by Victor Vroom, which suggests that individuals are motivated to perform well when they believe their efforts will lead to desired outcomes. In this case, the respondents' high ratings in various performances indicate their belief in the link between their efforts and positive outcomes, such as job satisfaction and recognition.

Overall, the data indicates a commendable level of performance among the respondents, reflecting positively on their capabilities and behaviours in the workplace.

Findings

On the demographic profile of the respondents, the findings are as follows: Based on the provided thesis data, here are the formulated findings:

- 1. Demographic Profile of Participants:** Most bread and pastry skills training program participants were relatively young, with three out of four falling within the 18-year-old age group. However, one participant stood older at 23, potentially offering a diverse perspective to the training sessions. Additionally, the program predominantly attracted female participants, reflecting underlying societal norms or interests in culinary pursuits among women within the community.
- 2. Civil Status and Educational Background:** All participants were noted as single, indicating that the training program may appeal to individuals without significant family responsibilities or commitments. There was also a mix of educational levels among the participants, with one individual having completed only elementary school while others had attained a high school education. This diversity in educational backgrounds highlights the inclusivity of the program, catering to individuals with varying levels of formal education.
- 3. Motivations for Joining the Program:** The purpose of joining the training program remained consistent across all participants, with a clear focus on acquiring bread and pastry skills. The majority expressed a desire to gain these skills for future employment opportunities, recognizing the practical value of culinary expertise in securing livelihoods. Additionally, one participant expressed interest in using the acquired skills to start a small-scale business, suggesting entrepreneurial aspirations within the cohort.
- 4. Internship Evaluation Results:** The internship evaluation results indicated a consistently high level of performance across various job-related and personality-related criteria. Participants received ratings of 4 or 5, indicating very satisfactory performance in job knowledge, quantity and quality of work, intelligence, cooperation, deportment, and attendance. These findings align with theories of job performance evaluation and organizational behaviour, emphasizing the significance

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Overall, the findings highlight the diverse yet unified motivations driving participants' participation in the training program and reflect positively on their capabilities and behaviours in the workplace. Such insights are invaluable for program organizers and stakeholders in tailoring future initiatives to meet the needs and interests of the target demographic better.

CONCLUSIONS

The Demographic Profile and Motivations: The demographic profile of participants in the bread and pastry skills training program reflects a diverse yet unified group, primarily comprising young, single individuals with varying educational backgrounds. The program predominantly attracted female participants, indicating potential societal norms or interests in culinary pursuits among women. Despite differences in age and educational levels, participants shared a common motivation for joining the program, with a clear focus on acquiring bread and pastry skills for future employment opportunities and entrepreneurial endeavours.

Inclusivity of the Program: The inclusivity of the training program is underscored by its ability to cater to individuals with varying levels of formal education. The mix of educational backgrounds among participants highlights the program's accessibility and capacity to provide opportunities for skill development to a wide range of individuals within the community.

Positive Performance Evaluation: The internship evaluation results revealed consistently high-performance levels among participants across various job-related and personality-related criteria. Participants demonstrated strong technical knowledge, productivity, professionalism, and cooperation in the workplace, reflecting positively on their capabilities and behaviours.

Alignment with Organizational Behavior Theories: The findings align with theories of organizational behaviour and job performance evaluation, emphasizing the importance of individual competencies, attitudes, and behaviours in determining job performance. Authors such as Peter Ducker, Douglas McGregor, and Victor Vroom support the results, emphasising the significance of employee motivation, skills, and behaviour in achieving organizational goals.

Implications for Program Development: The insights gained from the study have important implications for program organizers and stakeholders. Understanding the motivations and performance of participants can inform the development of future training initiatives, ensuring they effectively meet the needs and interests of the target demographic. Additionally, the upbeat performance evaluation results validate the effectiveness of the training program and highlight areas of strength to be maintained and built upon in future iterations.

Overall, the findings suggest that the bread and pastry skills training program successfully equips participants with valuable skills and fosters positive attitudes and behaviours in the workplace. Continued efforts to tailor program offerings to participants' needs and maintain high training and support standards are essential for maximizing the program's impact and ensuring the continued success of future initiatives.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations for Improving Future Trainees of the College of Hospitality Management Department's Outreach Program for Out-of-School Youth Beneficiaries:

1. **Targeted Outreach and Recruitment Strategies:** Develop outreach and recruitment strategies to reach more out-of-school youth beneficiaries. This may involve collaborating with local community organizations, schools, and youth centres to identify and engage potential participants who may benefit from the program.
2. **Comprehensive Needs Assessment:** Conduct a comprehensive needs assessment better to understand out-of-school youth beneficiaries' specific challenges and aspirations. This will help tailor program offerings to effectively address their unique needs, interests, and skill levels.
3. **Holistic Support Services:** Provide holistic support services to address the diverse needs of out-of-school youth beneficiaries, including academic support, career counselling, life skills training, and access to social services. By addressing the broader needs of participants, the program can better support their personal and professional development.
4. **Flexible Program Structures:** Offer flexible program structures to accommodate out-of-school youth beneficiaries' varying schedules and commitments. This may include offering evening or weekend classes, online learning options, and part-time internship opportunities to ensure accessibility and participation.
5. **Partnerships with Employers and Industry:** Forge partnerships with local employers and industry stakeholders to create internship and employment opportunities for program participants. Collaborating with employers can help ensure that program offerings are aligned with industry needs and provide participants with valuable real-world experience and job placement opportunities.
6. **Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation:** Implement a robust monitoring and evaluation framework to track the progress and outcomes of program participants systematically. Regular feedback and assessment will allow program organizers to identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments to enhance program effectiveness and impact.
7. **Long-Term Follow-Up and Alumni Engagement:** Establish a system for long-term follow-up and alums engagement to support program graduates' ongoing success and development. This may

include ongoing mentorship, networking opportunities, and access to continued education and training resources to support their career advancement and entrepreneurial aspirations.

By implementing these recommendations, the College of Hospitality Management Department's Outreach Program can better serve the needs of out-of-school youth beneficiaries and empower them to succeed in their personal and professional endeavours.

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